

Numerical analysis and successional relationships of shell-bed vegetation at Akerøya, Hvaler, SE Norway

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The vegetation of shell-beds is classified by association analysis and two different reallocation techniques. The outcomes of these techniques are evaluated by use of position vectors ordination. Association analysis followed by reallocation with untransformed Hult-Sernander-Du Rietz cover values proved superior, and was chosen as the basis for description of the vegetation. Groups were united into blocks, the main community unit of this study. The blocks are described and compared with communities described by Scandinavian authors. The successional relationships of the vegetation are discussed. Shore-line displacement, exposition, and influence of grazing are regarded as major factors determining the direction of the successions.

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Owing to richness in lime and other nutrients, shell deposits have a flora that is particularly interesting and rich in species. This has been the subject of study by botanists for many years (e.g. Størmer 1936, Hauge 1948, Ryvarden 1972). The vegetation of the shell-beds has, however, hitherto not been offered much attention in Norway. The only investigation that has been carried out is the one by Breien (1933), who described the plant communities in general terms and gave a good survey of the vascular plants characteristic to shell-beds in inner Østfold.

The floristically oriented works of Nilsson (1934, 1945) initiated the studies in the flora and vegetation on shell deposits along the west coast of Sweden. Further investigations were made by Hallberg (1959, 1965, 1971) and Hallberg & Ivarsson (1965). By far the most important is the one by Hallberg (1971) from Bohuslän, where the vegetation on shell deposits is classified in detail by the methods of the Zürich-Montpellier school.

Numerical methods have been in use in phytosociology for more than twenty years. A number of techniques have been extensively tested, and an impression of the major advantages and limitations associated with each of them is beginning to appear (Williams et al. 1966, Moore et al. 1970, Dale & Anderson 1972, Orłóci 1978a, Noy-Meir & Whittaker 1978, Whittaker & Gauch 1978). Numerical methods can roughly be divided into classification and ordination techniques. Much valuable informa-

tion has emerged from studies combining classification and ordination (Greig-Smith et al. 1967, Whittaker 1972, Noy-Meir & Whittaker 1977). There is no principal antagonism between the two approaches, and today they are accepted as complementary (Anderson 1965, Whittaker 1978a).

The traditional phytosociological methods applied by the Braun-Blanquet or Zürich-Montpellier school are not well suited for studies in vegetation without discontinuities (Shimwell 1971), and in a continually changing vegetation, discontinuities may be hard or even impossible to find. Numerical techniques have been applied with promising results, for example in the recent studies of Norwegian gletschervorfelds by Elven (1978) and Matthews (1979a, 1979b).

The aim of this investigation is to classify the vegetation of shell-beds at Akerøya, east of the Oslo fjord, by combining the approaches of classification and ordination and to relate the results to the major steps in the succession from naked shell-beds to species-rich pastures and dense scrub.

The investigation area

Geology, topography, and climate

Akerøya is situated east of the Oslo fjord in Østfold county, freely exposed to Skagerrak, and is one of the larger islands belonging to

Fig. 1. The position of Akerøya (ring) relative to the Oslo fjord.

Hvaler parish (Fig. 1). The estimated size of the island is 1.6 km² (Ryvarden 1972). The bedrock is of Precambrian age, mainly consisting of medium-grained Østfold granite containing approximately 75% SiO₂ (Barth 1960). The highest point is 32 m above sea level, but the greater part is lower than 20 m (Fig. 2). According to Danielsen (1970), the top of Akerøya first became dry land towards the end of the Atlantic period (circa 4000 years B.C.), while all of the present-day shell-beds are deposited after the beginning of the Subboreal period (3000 years B.C.).

Topographically, both sides of outer Oslo fjord are characterized by a fissure valley landscape (Naturgeografisk regioninndeling av Norden 1977). The main directions of the fissures at Akerøya are N-S and NE-SW. Most of the island is naked rock or covered with a thin layer of soil, but in depressions or other protected places, large quantities of shells are deposited. The lowest beds mainly contain shells of *Mytilus edulis*, not or hardly decomposed. Towards higher altitudes, the shell deposits become less concentrated because the shells are broken down and weathered away. The composition of molluscs also changes, and *Cardium edule*, *Mya arenaria*, *Patella vulgata*, *Ostrea edulis* and in particular different gastropod shells increase in frequency. In some beds the gastropods are totally dominating.

The influence of shells on the vegetation is due to their high lime content, giving high pH-values. Hallberg (1971) indicates pH=8.4 as an upper limit for shell-beds in Bohuslän and Breien (1933) has measured values in the range 8.4 to 8.6 in inner Østfold.

According to Naturgeografisk regioninndeling av Norden (1977), the investigated area belongs to the 'Coast areas off the Oslo fjord', a subregion of the Hemiboreal zone. The climate is

Table I. Meteorological data from Ferder (17 km W of Akerøya), Hvaler (of which Akerøya is a part) and Halden (30 km ENE of Akerøya).

Parameter	Station	Time interval	January	July	Year
Temperature	Ferder	1901 - 1960	- 0.5°C	+ 17.0°C	+ 7.3°C
	Halden	1901 - 1960	- 2.6°C	+ 17.4°C	+ 6.6°C
Precipitation	Ferder	1931 - 1960			725 mm
	Halden	1931 - 1960			729 mm
	Hvaler	1931 - 1960			696 mm

Fig. 2. The investigated shell-beds at Akerøya. Contour interval 10 m.

humid suboceanic with mild winters and relatively warm summers. The prevailing seasonal wind direction is N in winter, SW during the rest of the year (Johannessen 1960). Data on precipitation and temperature for some nearby stations are given in Table I.

Influence of man on the vegetation.

From pollen analyses in southern Østfold Danielsen (1970) estimated the start of agriculture in the area to be at the transition between the Atlantic and Subboreal periods

(circa 3000 years B.C.). Accordingly, Akerøya has probably been influenced by man since the first establishment of stable vegetation. A brief account of the history of man-made activities is given by Ryvarden (1972). A small farm, situated east on the island, was abandoned shortly after World War II. The central and north-eastern parts of the island have been cultivated. For the last thirty years, the island has been used for grazing, mostly by sheep, but in the first years after abandonment also by cattle. The grazing intensity has varied, and as many as 200 sheep have been grazing at Akerøya simultaneously. In

Fig. 3. The sampling at a shell-bed by use of a coordinate system. Dots indicate position of marking pegs.

1979 the number had decreased to 40. Every year the grazing starts primo May and lasts until ultimo November, the exact dates varying only slightly from year to year.

Materials and methods

The sampling scheme

The field work was carried out during May and June 1979. Consequently, some species of critical and late-flowering genera were impossible to

separate. These are treated collectively. Such taxa are *Allium oleraceum* and *A. vineale* (referred to as *Allium* spp.), *Rosa* spp., *Viola* spp. (including *V. rupestris*, *V. canina*, and *V. riviniana*), *Poa pratensis* coll. (including *P. pratensis* s.str., *P. irrigata*, and *P. angustifolia*), *Taraxacum* spp. (taxa belonging to the groups *Vulgaria*, *Erythrosperma*, and *Obliqua* were observed), *Euphrasia* spp., and *Hieracium pilosella* coll.

Most species of *Bryum* are impossible to separate in the sterile state, and are therefore treated collectively, except for *B. argenteum*. Hallberg (1971) gives a survey of *Bryum* species on shell deposits in Bohuslän.

Cladonia pyxidata coll. includes *C. pyxidata* s.str., *C. chlorophaea* and *C. pocillum*. *Cladonia arbuscula* coll. includes *C. arbuscula*, *C. impexa*, *C. mitis*, and *C. tenuis*.

Nomenclature of vascular plants follows Lid (1974), of mosses Nyholm (1954–69), of liverworts Arnell (1956), and of macrolichens Dahl & Krog (1973). Herbarium vouchers were collected of critical taxa, and will be deposited in O.

The contour lines of all dry shell-beds larger than approximately 300 m² were drawn onto a map. The 32 shell-beds satisfying these criteria are mapped in Fig. 2. The total area influenced by shell deposits was estimated to 0.08 km², or about 5% of the total area of Akerøya.

Restricted random sampling (Greig-Smith 1964) was chosen for the present study. It satisfies the demands on randomness set by the χ^2 -test of significance used in association analysis, and is easily applied to disjoint stands of vegetation.

The area of each of the 32 mapped shell-beds was calculated. One hundred sample plots (squares) were subjectively estimated to be sufficient to record the major variation within the vegetation, and the sample plots were distributed on the shell-beds in proportion to the area of the beds. The minimum number of plots in a bed was set to 2, the maximum number to 8. A coordinate system was indicated by pegs in each of the stands as shown in Fig. 3. The exact position of the plots was obtained from a table of random numbers (Owen 1962).

When plots are distributed at random, the fraction of heterogeneous plots increases with increasing plot size. Therefore, a conflict between representativity and homogeneity of the individual sample plot arises when the area of

the sample plots is to be decided upon. As the vegetation of shell-beds shows a mosaic pattern, the plot size has to be set low to give a representative picture of the individual plant communities. One square m was chosen as plot size for the present study. This size is subjectively estimated to be large enough to be representative for the analysed stands of vegetation (cf. Rodenberg 1976) and gave approximately 80% of homogeneous plots in the sense of Dahl (1957:29).

Within each plot, vascular plants, mosses, liverworts, and macrolichens were recorded. Crustose lichens were not included. Cover was assigned by the Hult-Sernander-Du Rietz cover scale (Du Rietz 1921).

According to Greig-Smith (1964), the association pattern is greatly influenced by plot size. Too small and too large plots both give results that may be difficult to interpret. The Zürich-Montpellier school uses a plot size larger than the minimal area, defined by Trass & Malmer (1978) and Westhoff & Maarel (1978) as the smallest representative area for the community in question. The existence of a minimal area and the methods used to determine it have been much debated (Goodall 1952, 1961). Estimation of minimal area in vegetation similar to the shell-bed vegetation of Akerøya is done by Sunding (1963) and Marker (1967), whose values are in the range 1.5–10 m². Ellenberg (1956) indicates a minimal area of 50–100 m² for central European xerothermous grassland communities.

In analyses of xerothermous vegetation with similarity to the vegetation on shell-beds at Akerøya, Marker (1967, 1969) used plot sizes ranging from 10 to 20 m², Hallberg (1971) from 0.25 to 100 m² and Rodenberg (1976) 1 m², while Ammar (1978), for numerical treatment of field and shrub layers separately, used 0.25 m² in the field layer and 4 m² in the shrub layer.

Numerical methods

For each method used a description of the method is given, and the arguments for the choice of that particular method are presented.

Association analysis. An outline of the method is given by Williams & Lambert (1959, 1960). As an index of association is used χ^2 with Yates' correction (Goodall 1978a). As rare species increase the computation work strongly without giving important contributions to the classification, only the 81 species that occur in 8

or more plots are taken into account. All significant associations at the 0.05 significance level are noted. Positive and negative associations are considered of equal value. $\Sigma\chi^2$ is calculated for each of the 81 species. The species with the highest $\Sigma\chi^2$ -value is used to divide the set of 100 plots into two subsets according to its presence or absence. The process is repeatedly applied to each of the subsets and to sets of lower order until none of the species in any of the groups are involved in more than one significant association. Consequently, the criterion used in the divisive process is monothetic (Goodall 1978b). The resulting groups will be referred to as ASS-groups.

All calculations have been made by hand on a SANYO CZ-2901 Scientific Calculator.

Reallocation. Association analysis satisfies most of the criteria for a suitable classification, but is susceptible to serious misclassifications (Hill et al. 1975). One way to discover and correct such misclassifications is to reexamine the classes for their membership and perform a reallocation of the misplaced plots (Orlóci 1978a). This is commonly done *in series* with agglomerative clustering techniques (e.g. Bradfield & Orłóci 1975, Matthews 1979a).

In the mathematical model forming the basis for multivariate analysis of plant communities, the n plots can be represented as points in a m -dimensional space. Each of the m species defines one axis, and the loadings on the axes correspond to cover values or other importance values (Orlóci 1978b). Accordingly, the j -th plot can be represented as a vector in R^{81} on the form $x_j = (a_{1j}, \dots, a_{ij}, \dots, a_{81j})$

where a_{ij} is the cover value for species i in plot j .

A sample space (Orlóci 1978a, 1978b) is constructed by defining an index of similarity between samples. Here a scalar product is used standardized by plot norms, an expression that reflects the degree of correlation between the plots (Orlóci 1978a). The scalar product between plots x_i and x_j is expressed $q_{x_i x_j}$. This index can be interpreted as the cosine of the angle between the compared plots in the sample space (e.g. Apostol 1969). Its corresponding distance measure shows much the same properties as the extensively used Euclidean distance (Orlóci 1978a).

Group centroids are calculated for all the ASS-groups by finding the arithmetic mean of the cover values of all species in the plots that

belong to the group. The group centroid of ASS-group j is referred to as $\bar{x}_j$.

The reallocation procedure used is iterative (Matthews 1979a) and the algorithm is as follows:

(1) $q_{x_i x_j}$ is calculated.

(2) Translocation of all plots x_i (belonging to ASS-group j) for which the following criteria are satisfied:

(a) $q_{x_i x_k} > q_{x_i x_j}$.

(b) $q_{x_i, \bar{x}_k} > q_{x_i, \bar{x}_j}$ for all $p = 1, 2, \dots, n$ (number of ASS-groups), $p \neq k$.

(3) New group centroids are calculated for the groups so obtained.

(4) The process (1) to (3) is repeated until all groups are stable.

Ideally, new group centroids should be calculated after each translocation (Matthews 1979a), but this is too laborious when calculations are made by hand. In fact, the results from the two algorithms will be nearly identical.

The effect of the characteristics of the cover scale upon the performance of a similarity measure is potentially great (Goodall 1978a). As a consequence of this, two different cover scales are here used in reallocation, (1) untransformed Hult-Sernander-Du Rietz cover values, giving a set of groups that are referred to as RE-groups, (2) square root transformation of the Hult-Sernander-Du Rietz cover values, giving a set of RER-groups.

Evaluation of similarity between the corresponding groups from the different reallocation procedures is done by calculating percent correspondence between the groups.

$$\text{Percent correspondence} = \frac{2A}{B+C} \cdot 100$$

where A is the number of plots common to the compared groups, B and C are the total number of plots in each of the groups. The formula is analogous to Sørensen's 'coefficient of community' for comparison of plots (Sørensen 1948).

As the scalar product squares the cover values, the reallocation with untransformed data will put more weight on dominants, while the square root transformation more strongly emphasizes overall floristic composition of the compared entities (Whittaker & Gauch 1978).

Ordination. The application of ordination to a phytosociological data set is an attempt to structure the data set by reducing the dimensionality of the sample space from m to m^* variables

(Cormack 1971). Mostly, the major purpose of ordinations has been extraction of ecologically interpretable axes – ecological ordination (Whittaker & Gauch 1978). However, ordination can also serve to display similarity (or 'distance') between plant communities, that is to serve a classificatory purpose (Noy-Meir & Whittaker 1978). When used in this way, the ordination is referred to as taxometric (Whittaker & Gauch 1978). One of the major problems of ecological ordination is that most of the widely used techniques extract linear, orthogonal axes while most coenoclines show a non-linear relation to the axes (Orlóci 1978b, Whittaker & Gauch 1978). This causes curvilinear distortion and makes the axes hard to interpret (Whittaker & Gauch 1978, Noy-Meir & Whittaker 1978).

In the present study, position vectors ordination or PVO (Orlóci 1966, 1978a, 1978b) is used. It is a simplified principal components analysis (PCA) algorithm which is strongly subject to curvilinear distortion (Whittaker & Gauch 1978), but provides an optimal scattering of the entities on the ordination axes (Orlóci 1978a). PVO is applied to RER- and RE-group centroids *in parallel*, thus giving two independent ordinations. Non-centering of data is used as recommended by Noy-Meir (1973). The ordination is based on correlation between plots. The ordination axes are chosen as those group centroids being able to extract the largest amount of variability in a secondary matrix of scalar products between group centroids standardized by norms. Accordingly, they are the optimal approximation by group centroids to the eigenvector axes of PCA. This approximation is more favourable when the number of ordinated entities increases (Orlóci 1978b).

After extraction of position vectors, loadings for the 100 plots on each of the axes in both ordinations were calculated. On the basis of these plot scores, some useful statistics were calculated:

$\bar{x}_{ij}$ the mean of the loadings of plots in group i (a particular ASS-, RER- or RE-group) along axis j .

q_{ijw} the variance of the loadings of plots in group i along axis j .

Q_{iw} the sum of q_{ijw} taken over all groups belonging to the same classification set ('variance within groups' when used in variance analysis (e.g. Sverdrup 1973)).

Q_{jb} the variance of the group means (groups

belonging to the same classification set) relative to the mean of the scores for the 100 squares along the axis in question ('variance between groups').

Results

Association analysis

The significant associations in the set of the 81 most frequent species are summarized in Table II. A diagram showing the divisions in association analysis is given in Fig. 4. Application of the previously defined stopping rule (p. 75) gave 13 ASS-groups.

The first division is based on *Sedum acre*, having $\Sigma\chi^2 = 414.12$. This division is ecologically meaningful and easily interpreted as *Sedum acre* is a character species (in the sense of Westhoff & Maarel (1978)) for the class Sedo-Scleranthetea of the phytosociological hierarchy of the Zürich-Montpellier school. This class mostly contains pioneer vegetation on rock or shallow soil. Consequently, the first division occurs along the lines previously recognized by subjective methods (e.g. Hallberg 1971), and divides the data set into a pioneer group and a group of later successional stages.

Division of the + *Sedum acre* set of plots is by *Ditrichum flexicaule* at moderately high $\Sigma\chi^2$ -level; $\Sigma\chi^2 = 48.65$. This species is a differential species between the two Sedo-Scleranthetea alliances, *Koelerion albescentis* and *Tortello-Sedion*, occurring in the latter of the two (Hallberg 1971). Consequently, the group with *Ditrichum flexicaule* is a pioneer group on exposed rocks with scattered shells deposited in crevices. The - *Ditrichum flexicaule* group, however, which is quite heterogeneous, is divided at $\Sigma\chi^2 = 19.13$ by *Festuca ovina*, separating a group of halophilous pioneer vegetation without *Festuca ovina* on recently colonized shell-beds close to the sea, and a group with *Festuca ovina*.

Division of the - *Sedum acre* group occurs at high $\Sigma\chi^2$ -level, $\Sigma\chi^2 = 278.56$, and is effected by *Carex caryophyllea*. According to Hallberg (1971) the species is confined to the 'Trockerasengesellschaften' of the alliance Mesobromion, in which it is a character species. According to Rodenberg (1976) *Carex caryophyllea* is preferential character species for 'mesophile Trockenrasen' at central Öland. The

Table II. Main characteristics of the division by association-analysis.

	Number	Percentage
Species occurring in ≥ 8 sites	81	
Possible combinations	3240	
Significant associations at the 0.05 level	670	20.68
Significant positive associations at the 0.05 level	462	14.26
Significant negative associations at the 0.05 level	208	6.42
Significant associations at the 0.01 level	345	10.65
Significant positive associations at the 0.01 level	251	7.75
Significant negative associations at the 0.01 level	94	2.90

+ *Carex caryophyllea* group is well defined, and internally rather homogeneous. Division of the group occurs at $\Sigma\chi^2 = 23.79$, and this, as well as further subdivisions, is hard to interpret.

Division of the - *Carex caryophyllea* group is by *Campyllum chrysophyllum* at $\Sigma\chi^2 = 95.28$. Hallberg (1971) states that the species has a wide ecological amplitude on shell deposits in Bohuslän, and the groups are not easy to interpret by means of the dividing species. Further division of the + *Campyllum chrysophyllum* group occurs at low $\Sigma\chi^2$.

The - *Campyllum chrysophyllum* group is not only a residual group in the classification, but may be interpreted as a climax group, dominated by *Juniperus communis* that has invaded the pastures after grazing has ceased.

Division of the group is effected by *Melica nutans* and *Hepatica nobilis*, both having $\Sigma\chi^2 = 17.61$. This group contains more typical climax vegetation than the - group, which may be interpreted as a residual group although it mainly contains plots that belong to the climax vegetation of *Juniperus* scrub. The occurrence of such a residual group is one of the main objections to a monothetic classification method.

Reallocation

Reallocation was effected by both scales of cover values (see p. 76) at two levels of resolution; the 5-group level and the 13-group level. The first of these corresponds to terminated division in association analysis at a level of $\Sigma\chi^2 = 40$.

Percent correspondence values (p. 76) for reallocation on the 5-group level are given in Table III.

Fig. 4. Division by association analysis. The figures in the dendrogram give the number of plots at each level of division. Abbreviations: A.s. - *Arenaria serpyllifolia*, C.j. - *Centaurea jacea*, C.r. - *Campanula rotundifolia*, H.n. - *Hepatica nobilis*, M.n. - *Melica nutans*, P.s. - *Pimpinella saxifraga*, T.sp. - *Taraxacum spp.*

Table III. Percentage correspondence between ASS-, RER- and RE-groups at the 5-group level.

Group No.	No. of plots in			Percentage correspondence		
	ASS-gr.	RER-gr.	RE-gr.	ASS/RER	ASS/RE	RER/RE
1	7	7	9	86	67	75
2	16	17	16	91	81	91
3	35	34	35	87	86	93
4	21	16	11	65	44	67
5	21	26	29	77	72	95

Table IV. Percentage correspondence between ASS-, RER- and RE-groups at the 13-group level.

Group No.	No. of plots in			Percentage correspondence		
	ASS-gr.	RER-gr.	RE-gr.	ASS/RER	ASS/RE	RER/RE
1	7	7	5	86	83	83
2	6	6	5	100	91	91
3	10	11	12	95	91	96
4	11	10	11	95	91	95
5	6	6	5	100	73	73
6	12	12	9	92	86	86
7	6	6	8	100	86	86
8	4	6	8	80	67	86
9	9	7	6	88	80	92
10	8	9	5	94	77	71
11	10	10	13	90	78	78
12	3	3	3	100	100	100
13	8	7	10	67	33	59

Groups 1 (containing group 1 at the 13-group level), 2 (containing groups 2 and 3), and 3 (containing groups 4 to 7 at the 13-group level) are stable under both of the reallocation procedures. This indicates that the groups are well delimited, but implies nothing about the homogeneity within each group.

Group 4 (containing groups 8 to 10 at the 13-group level) is decimated by reallocation, most strongly when applied to untransformed cover data. The reason is observed when groups 4 and 5 (the latter containing groups 11 to 13 at the 13-group level) are examined simultaneously. Most of the plots that are removed from group 4 are translocated to group 5. This is caused by the internal heterogeneity of group 4, containing both *Festuca ovina*- and *Juniperus communis*-dominated plots. The *Juniperus communis* dominance types (Whittaker 1978c) are translocated in reallocation, most efficiently by untransformed cover data because of the higher relative weight given to dominance.

Percent correspondence values for realloca-

tion at the 13-group level are given in Table IV.

The pattern observed at the 5-group level reappears. Reallocation with untransformed cover data produces groups (RE-groups) that are more easily interpreted as dominance types than the groups produced by reallocation with root transformed cover data (RER-groups). The number of reallocated plots is also different; 9 with root transformation and 22 without.

Among the 13 ASS-groups, 8 are stable under both reallocations (percentage correspondence >80% in both cases). These are groups 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, and 12.

Groups 5 and 10 are transformed to *Juniperus communis* dominance-types by reallocation with untransformed data. ASS-group 13 is highly heterogeneous, being a residual group with plots that lack all of the dividing species in association analysis. Only the reallocation based on untransformed cover data is capable of creating a homogeneous *Juniperus communis* dominance type from the residual group.

Table V. Percentage variability accounted for by the axes of the two ordinations.

Component No.	Ordination based on RER-group centroids		Ordination based on RE-group centroids	
	variability accounted for	cumulative	variability accounted for	cumulative
1	60.95	60.95	52.95	52.95
2	9.78	70.73	17.61	70.56
3	9.37	80.10	10.41	80.97

Ordination

Ordination was effected at the 13-group level. Both ordinations (based on RE- and RER-group centroids, respectively) gave the following position vectors:

- (1) first position vector - $\bar{x}_6$
- (2) second position vector - $\bar{x}_{11}$
- (3) third position vector - $\bar{x}_3$

where $\bar{x}_j$ means centroid of RE-group j in the ordination based on untransformed cover values, the centroid of RER-group j in ordination with square root transformed cover values.

The variability accounted for by the different position vectors is given in Table V. Further axes were found, but as they were impossible to interpret, only the first 3 axes are dealt with here.

Ordination of RER-group centroids based on root transformation of cover values:

(1) The first axis accounts for 60.95% of the total variability of the set of RER-group centroids. The loadings on this axis refer to the degree of correlation with the RER-group 6 centroid. This is high in plots in which the typical 'Halbtrockenrasen' species (see Hallberg 1971, Rodenborg 1976 and pp. 87-89) play an important role. RER-groups 4 to 9 have the highest loadings, while both the pioneer groups 1 to 3 and the climax groups 10 to 13 have lower loadings.

(2) The second axis is RER-group centroid 11, accounting for 9.78% of the total variability. High scores are obtained by the climax groups 10 to 13, partly also 5, while group 7 gets the lowest value.

(3) The third position vector (axis) accounts for 9.37% of the total variability. RER-group centroid 3 has great occurrence of halophytes and species that withstand competition poorly, giving high loadings to the pioneer groups 1 to 3.

Axes of higher order all account for less than

4% of the total variability, and only give high loadings to plots within the group whose centroid is the position vector defining the axis. They therefore have no ecological significance.

Ordination of RE-group centroids based on untransformed cover values gives three axes that are interpreted much the same way as in the first ordination. However, one important difference should be noted. The variability accounted for by the second axis is rather high (17.61%) at the expense of the first axis (52.95%). This makes a more distinct scattering of the groups along the second axis than in the first ordination. The reason is the greater emphasis on dominance in reallocation, producing more clearcut *Juniperus communis* dominance types. This is accentuated by use of untransformed data in ordination.

A taxogram for this ordination is given in Fig. 5, where the mean of the scores for the plots belonging to the same group and the corresponding standard deviations are given.

Discussion

Evaluation of classification and ordination techniques

According to Matthews (1979b), classification assumes a difference in kind, ordination a difference in degree. Even so, most present workers hold that there is nothing to prevent classification in a continuum (bibliography is given by Orlóci 1978b), and that the apparent contradiction between the two approaches is a controversy over a non-existent problem (Anderson 1965, Whittaker 1978a).

The problem of evaluating the outcomes of different numerical treatments of vegetation data is associated with the complexity of the underlying variables (species) and the often intricate mathematical formulas that are part of the tech-

niques (Beals 1973). To make the interpretation easier, I have employed the mathematically simplest of the available and acceptable methods for this study.

The test of association analysis by Hill et al. (1975) can be summarized as follows:

(1) Association analysis produces ecologically meaningful and easily interpretable groups in heterogeneous data sets.

(2) It is an open classification technique; new entities are easily placed into the recognized groups.

(3) Simple calculations.

(4) Susceptible to serious misclassifications.

Williams & Lambert (1959, 1960) point out that the criterion used in the process of division, $\max \Sigma \chi^2$ based on significant associations, will maximize the effect of the subdivisions within the resulting groups. The reason why misclassifications can, and do, occur in spite of this is to be searched for in the relation of the individual species to the communities. From phytosociological research with the methods of the Zürich-Montpellier school (Westhoff & Maarel 1978) it is known that few species are absolute constants in one community or a group of communities while they never occur in others. Conversely, the character species are mostly rare species with low frequency. In the species-poor flora of Scandinavia, character species are rarely found at lower levels of the phytosociological hierarchy (Trass & Malmer 1978). When the relations between species and community types are as described, occasional spurious divisions must be expected to occur (cf. Ivimey-Cook 1972). In spite of these drawbacks, association analysis does function fairly well in species-rich vegetation (Noy-Meir et al. 1970). This is a consequence of the number of species to species relations, which is proportional with the square of the number of species in the data set.

Evaluation of the results from the different classification and ordination approaches assumes an underlying set of criteria for 'goodness'. A set of criteria for evaluation of results from a classification in numerical taxonomy (Williams & Dale 1965) might well be used in this context:

The classification aims at defining a set of classes in which (1) members of the same class shall be 'as like as possible', and (2) members of different classes shall be 'as unlike as possible'.

Fig. 5. Position of the RE-groups relative to the axes extracted by use of position vectors ordination with untransformed cover values, (a) the first two axes, (b) the first and the third axis. Centre of the circles indicates the mean of the loadings for the plots belonging to the group in question. Horizontal and vertical bars represent standard deviation along the axes.

A third criterion regarding interpretability of the classes in ecological terms could be added. This will not be independent of the two criteria cited above, because the groups that best satisfy the criteria of Williams & Dale (1965) are most often also the easiest to interpret.

The meaning of 'as like as' and 'as unlike as' can be defined precisely by using a measure of distance. For this purpose, the taxometric ordination might be used. The imperfection of any ordination technique must then first be emphasized.

A good classification, judged by the criteria of Williams & Dale (1965), has a high variance between groups (Q_{jb}), which means groups that are well separated, and a low value of variance

Table VI. Ordination axes based on RER-group centroids. Variance within groups (Q_{jw}), between groups (Q_{jb}) and quotient Q_j for ASS-, RER- and RE-groups.

Axis	ASS-groups			RER-groups			RE-groups		
	$\bar{x}_6$	$\bar{x}_{11}$	$\bar{x}_3$	$\bar{x}_6$	$\bar{x}_{11}$	$\bar{x}_3$	$\bar{x}_6$	$\bar{x}_{11}$	$\bar{x}_3$
Variance within groups (Q_{jw})	0.74	2.04	1.44	0.79	1.25	0.80	0.76	0.99	0.51
Variance between groups (Q_{jb})	2.26	5.32	5.36	2.23	4.98	5.94	2.25	5.20	6.53
$Q_j = Q_{jb}/Q_{jw}$	3.05	2.61	3.72	2.82	3.98	7.43	2.96	5.25	12.80

Table VII. Ordination axes based on RE-group centroids. Variance within groups (Q_{jw}), between groups (Q_{jb}) and quotient Q_j for ASS-, RER- and RE-groups.

Axis	ASS-groups			RER-groups			RE-groups		
	$\bar{x}_6$	$\bar{x}_{11}$	$\bar{x}_3$	$\bar{x}_6$	$\bar{x}_{11}$	$\bar{x}_3$	$\bar{x}_6$	$\bar{x}_{11}$	$\bar{x}_3$
Variance within groups (Q_{jw})	1.58	4.87	1.91	1.87	3.44	1.30	0.95	1.49	0.78
Variance between groups (Q_{jb})	4.00	8.24	5.57	4.76	9.57	6.49	4.56	11.13	6.49
$Q_j = Q_{jb}/Q_{jw}$	2.53	1.69	2.92	2.55	2.78	4.99	4.80	7.47	8.32

within groups (Q_{jw}), which means groups that are internally homogeneous. The criteria can be tested simultaneously by the index

$$Q_j = \frac{Q_{jb}}{Q_{jw}}$$

Q_{jw} , Q_{jb} and Q_j are tabulated in Tables VI and VII, where the two ordinations are treated separately.

In the ordination with untransformed cover data, RE-groups give the best results. The variance within groups is lowest for all three axes, and the variance between groups is highest for two of the axes. For the axis based on $\bar{x}_6$, there is but a slight difference between the three classifications. For all axes, the Q_j -values of the RE-groups are the highest. The RE-groups must be regarded as best, the ASS-groups as least satisfactory, and the RER-groups as intermediate when evaluated by the criteria of Williams & Dale (1965).

The ordination with cover data transformed by square root gives approximately the same results; again the Q_j -values of the RER-groups are lying between those of RE-groups and ASS-groups. Along the first ordination axis, $\bar{x}_6$, the Q_j -values are, however, rather close to each

other and the differences between them cannot be regarded as significant.

The conclusion is that the RE-groups are the best separated and most homogeneous groups among the three group sets. This is invariant under the two ordination techniques. Accordingly, the conclusion is valid irrespective of emphasizing dominance or overall floristic composition. The reliability of the results of this evaluation should be seen in relation to the methods used. As linear techniques such as PVO are accepted as optimal summarizers of relationships (Kessell & Whittaker 1976, Orlóci 1978a, 1978b), they must also be expected to be optimal for comparison of classifications by means of ordination results.

Interpretation of RE-vegetation units

The ultimate goal of numerical treatment of vegetation data is the production of interpretable results (Whittaker 1962, 1978b, 1978c). Among the three sets of groups obtained by association analysis and reallocation, the RE-groups proved superior (p. 82), at least regarding delimitation and internal homogeneity of the groups.

The RE-groups have proved to be easy to

0.765	2																		
0.524	0.679	3																	
0.780	0.644	0.297	4																
0.648	0.620	0.259	0.800	5															
0.744	0.664	0.267	0.915	0.797	6														
0.740	0.643	0.270	0.878	0.752	0.911	7													
0.666	0.524	0.157	0.783	0.684	0.788	0.709	8												
0.685	0.647	0.231	0.792	0.761	0.841	0.801	0.791	9											
0.435	0.443	0.147	0.543	0.594	0.610	0.463	0.704	0.583	10										
0.239	0.288	0.077	0.265	0.394	0.355	0.221	0.449	0.313	0.876	11									
0.532	0.512	0.224	0.647	0.708	0.699	0.580	0.660	0.654	0.824	0.703	12								
0.351	0.411	0.265	0.373	0.449	0.447	0.337	0.445	0.367	0.852	0.891	0.708	13							

Fig. 6. Scalar product between RE-group centroids standardized by norms.

relate to ecological factors, communities described by other authors, and successional stages. Some of the groups can, however, hardly be regarded as distinct communities and are therefore subjectively united to form blocks, as done by Galten (1977). Scalar products divided by norms for all RE-group centroids are calculated to show the degree of similarity between the groups. They are presented in Fig. 6.

Grouping of vegetation units produced by numerical techniques into blocks facilitate interpretability. The blocks are the ultimate community types of this study. The highly heterogeneous RE-group 12 containing 3 plots is distributed on the groups that the plots resemble most closely as determined by the highest $q_{x_i, \bar{x}_j}$ -values.

The RE-based blocks show a high degree of similarity with communities on the same substrate in Bohuslän (Hallberg 1971). Points of resemblance are found to vegetation on calcareous grassland by the Oslo fjord (Sunding 1963, 1965, Marker 1967, 1969) and in the Gudbrandsdalen valley (Kleiven 1959), to the alvar vegetation on southern Öland (Albertson 1950) and in Västergötland (Albertson 1946), and to the abandoned calcareous pastures on central Öland described by Rodenberg (1976). Emphasis is placed on a comparison with the main vegetation units of these works (associations, 'communities' etc.), as higher units (especially orders and alliances of the Zürich-Montpellier school) are subject to much discussion, and generally accepted definitions have not yet been reached

(Pignatti 1968, Dierschke 1971). An extensive comparison with plant communities described by central European investigators is considered beyond the scope of this work. For this subject, as well as for a survey of the phytosociological hierarchy, the reader is referred to Hallberg (1971).

The blocks are numbered so as to reflect the main lines along the successional gradients. Table VIII gives a survey of the blocks and their differential species. Species occurring only in one block can be regarded as local, preferential character species for the block (cf. Dahl 1957, Westhoff & Maarel 1978) in the vegetation of shell-beds at Akerøya.

Block I (including RE-group No. 3). Block I occurs as a pioneer community in a narrow zone about 1-2 m above sea level (Fig. 7), and is the first community to colonize the *Mytilus edulis* beds. The vegetation is mostly closed (Fig. 8), but becomes more scattered towards lower altitudes and towards the sea. According to Hallberg (1971), the community is never directly exposed to sea spray.

Because of the shallow soil, the community is poor in species. The dominating species in the field layer is always *Festuca rubra*, but sometimes *Bromus hordeaceus* appears as subdominant. Constants (occurring in 81-100% of the plots) are *Sedum acre* and *Arenaria serpyllifolia*. The bottom layer is characterized by dominance of *Hypnum cupressiforme* and *Bryum* spp. Mosses with a wide ecological amplitude, such as *Amblystegium serpens*, *Ceratodon purpureus*,

Table VIII. Synopsis of species composition of RE-groups and RE-based blocks. Constancy % and characteristic degree of cover (Persson 1961) are tabulated.

Block No.	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII						
RE-group No.	3	2	1	9	8	4	7	6	5	10	13	11	
Number of plots	12	5	5	6	8	11	8	9	6	6	10	14	
<i>Armeria maritima</i>	67-1	20-1							17-1		10-1		
<i>Cochlearia officinalis</i>	42-1	20-1											
<i>Potentilla anserina</i>	8-1												
<i>Amblystegium serpens</i>	42-1											7-1	
<i>Artemisia campestris</i>		20-1	20-2										
<i>Erigeron acre</i>	17-1		40-1										
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	50-2	60-1		17-1		9-1	50-1		17-1		10-1		
<i>Bromus hordeaceus</i>	33-3	40-1	20-1					11-1					
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	100-4	80-2	60-1		13-1					17-1	50-1		
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	58-1	40-1	60-1	17-2		9-1			33-1				
<i>Tortula ruralis</i>	67-1		80-1				38-1						
<i>Potentilla argentea</i>	25-1	40-1	20-1	33-1					11-1				
<i>Sagina nodosa</i>	17-1		60-1	17-1									
<i>Sedum acre</i>	92-2	100-1	100-1	17-1	13-1								
<i>Sedum album</i>	42-1	40-1	60-1	33-1	25-1			13-1					
<i>Arenaria serpyllifolia</i>	100-1	100-1	80-1		63-1	18-1	63-1	33-1	17-1		10-1	14-1	
<i>Cerastium semidecandrum</i>	42-1	100-1	20-1	17-1	13-1	9-1	25-1	22-1	33-1				
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	42-1	20-1	80-1	50-1	38-1	73-1	50-1	44-1	17-1	17-1			
<i>Saxifraga tridactylites</i>	25-1	20-1	20-1	17-1		9-1	25-1	11-1	17-1				
<i>Bryum argenteum</i>	42-1		60-1	67-1	13-1	55-1	50-1	22-1					
<i>Cornicularia aculeata</i>	17-1	60-1	80-1		13-1	64-1	25-1	11-1	17-1				
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	58-2	100-1	100-2	67-1	50-1	100-2	75-1	100-1	100-1	100-1	60-1	21-1	
<i>Cerastium fontanum</i>	33-1		20-1		25-1	55-1	25-1	67-1	50-1	83-1	60-1	43-1	
<i>Galium verum</i>	58-1	60-1	60-1	33-2	50-1	100-2	75-1	89-2	100-1	67-1	70-1	36-1	
<i>Hornungia petraea</i>	8-1		60-1		75-1	9-1	63-1	33-1	33-1	50-1	10-1	36-1	
<i>Taraxacum spp.</i>	75-1	100-1	80-1	100-1	38-1	73-1	100-1	67-1	17-1		60-1		
<i>Thalictrum minus</i>	33-1	40-1	20-1	17-1	38-1	64-1	38-1	56-1	50-1	50-1	40-1	71-1	
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	33-1	40-1	20-1	33-1		36-1	75-1	44-1	17-1		20-1		
<i>Poa pratensis coll.</i>	33-2		20-1			9-1	38-1		33-1		40-2		
<i>Barbula convoluta</i>	8-1	40-3	80-2	100-2	100-1	82-1	100-2	89-1	50-2	100-1	60-1	21-1	
<i>Bryum spp.</i>	83-2	80-1	60-1	100-1	100-1	100-2	88-1	78-1	100-1	83-1	70-1	14-1	
<i>Hypnum cupressiforme</i>	83-4	80-3	100-2	83-1	13-1	91-2	88-1	89-2	93-2	67-1	60-3	50-1	
<i>Tortella tortuosa</i>	8-1	40-3		67-1	75-1	18-2	13-1	44-1	17-1	83-1		64-1	
<i>Cetraria islandica</i>	17-1	60-1	20-1	33-1	13-1	27-1	50-1	33-1	17-1	17-1	10-1	7-2	
<i>Anthyllis vulneraria</i>		40-1	40-1	67-1		73-1	50-2	22-1	17-1	17-1			
<i>Satureja acinos</i>	8-1	60-1	80-1	100-1	88-1	55-1	38-1	56-1	33-1	17-1	10-1		
<i>Cladonia foliacea</i>		20-1	20-1			9-1	13-1	33-1					
<i>Erophila verna</i>		100-1		50-1		9-1	38-1	11-1	17-1				
<i>Festuca ovina</i>		100-3	100-4	100-4	100-4	100-4	100-5	100-5	100-4	100-2	50-1	57-1	
<i>Antennaria dioica</i>		20-1		80-1	100-1	88-2	100-2	50-3	89-2	67-2	83-2	30-1	29-1
<i>Distichium capillaceum</i>				40-1	17-1	50-1			11-1		33-1		7-1
<i>Ditrichum flexicaule</i>	8-1			100-2	17-1	88-1	55-3	13-1	33-1	17-1	50-1		14-1
<i>Encalypta streptocarpa</i>				20-1		50-1	27-1				33-1	10-1	7-1
<i>Myurella julacea</i>				20-1	17-1	50-1	18-1	13-1	22-1	17-1	17-1		
<i>Allium spp.</i>				17-1	13-1		18-1	38-1	22-1				
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>				33-1	50-1				22-1		17-1		
<i>Saxifraga granulata</i>				17-1				13-1	11-1				
<i>Scleranthus perennis</i>					13-1			13-1	11-1				
<i>Calamagrostis epigeios</i>				17-1					22-2				
<i>Tortella fragilis</i>					38-1		18-1	13-1	11-1				
<i>Weisia controversa</i>				17-1			9-1						
<i>Hieracium pilosella coll.</i>		40-1	20-1	17-1	88-1	91-1	50-1	67-1	50-1	17-1		7-1	
<i>Hypochoeris maculata</i>				17-1		36-1	13-1		33-1				
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>				83-1		27-1	50-1	22-1	50-1		10-1		
<i>Rosa spp.</i>					13-1			22-1	17-1	17-1	20-1		
<i>Rubus saxatilis</i>				17-2	38-1	9-1			50-1	33-2	30-1	36-1	
<i>Campanula rotundifolia</i>		20-1	20-1	33-1	100-1	82-1	13-1	100-1	33-1	83-1	60-1	50-1	
<i>Centaurea jacea</i>			20-1		75-1	91-1		22-1	33-1	50-1	10-1	21-1	
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>				17-1	25-1	18-1	13-1	11-1	33-1	17-1		29-1	
<i>Linum catharticum</i>				83-1	50-1	27-1	13-1	56-1		83-1	60-1	43-1	
<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i>		20-1	20-1	33-1	63-1	100-1			83-1	83-1	60-1	43-1	
<i>Vicia cracca</i>				17-1	13-1	9-1	38-1	33-1	33-1		30-1	7-1	
<i>Viola spp.</i>					38-1	55-1	50-1	44-1	50-1	17-1		21-1	
<i>Briza media</i>				17-1	38-1	55-1	25-1	33-1	17-1	33-1		14-1	
<i>Carex ericetorum</i>				50-1	75-1	55-2	25-2	56-2	67-1		67-1	14-1	
<i>Carex flacca</i>		20-1	20-2	67-1	88-2	55-2	50-2	56-1	67-1	100-1	20-1	71-1	
<i>Campylium chrysophyllum</i>	8-1			100-1	100-1	36-1	25-1	56-1	33-1	83-1	30-1	7-1	
<i>Dicranum scoparium</i>	8-1	20-1		100-2	25-1	55-2	25-3	67-2	100-1	67-1	10-1	29-2	
<i>Fissidens cristatus</i>		20-1	20-1	100-1	88-2	82-1	100-1	89-1	100-1	100-1	90-1	86-1	
<i>Cladonia pyxidata coll.</i>				33-2	75-1	27-1	25-1	44-1	17-1	83-1	10-1	43-1	
<i>Cladonia arbuscula coll.</i>				33-1		18-1	13-1	22-1	33-2	50-1		14-1	

Table VIII (continued).

Block No.	I	II	III	IV		V			VI	VII		
RE-group No.	3	2	1	9	8	4	7	6	5	10	13	11
Number of plots	12	5	5	6	8	11	8	9	6	6	10	14
<i>Plantago media</i>				17-1		27-1	25-1	22-1	17-1			7-1
<i>Camptothecium lutescens</i>	17-2	20-1	80-1		25-2	91-2	100-3	78-2	33-2	50-1	60-1	14-1
<i>Climacium dendroides</i>	8-2					18-2	50-1					
<i>Rhytidium rugosum</i>					13-1	9-1	50-1	67-1				
<i>Ranunculus acris</i>						9-1	50-1		17-1			
<i>Arrhenatherum pratense</i>				33-2	50-1	73-1	100-1	78-1	67-1			7-1
<i>Carex caryophylla</i>			20-1			100-2	88-1	100-1	83-1		30-1	
<i>Luzula campestris</i>				17-1		27-1	38-1	44-1	50-1			
<i>Arabis hirsuta</i>	8-1	20-1		17-1	25-1	36-1	50-1	78-1		67-1	70-1	14-1
<i>Thymus pulegioides</i>		20-1	20-1	33-1		36-1	50-1	22-3	50-1	67-1	20-1	14-1
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>						18-1		11-1	33-1	17-1	20-1	7-1
<i>Arrhenatherum pubescens</i>		20-1				18-1	50-1	22-1	17-1	33-1	30-1	
<i>Rhodryum roseum</i>							25-1	11-1	17-1		10-1	
<i>Juniperus communis</i>		20-3	20-2	33-2	50-2	9-1		33-2	83-3	100-5	100-5	100-5
<i>Galium boreale</i>						9-1			50-1		30-1	14-1
<i>Geranium sanguineum</i>					25-1	9-1		11-1	67-1	50-1	10-1	50-1
<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i>									17-1		20-1	
<i>Carex digitata</i>									17-2	83-1	10-1	57-1
<i>Neckera complanata</i>					13-1				17-3	33-2	10-2	36-2
<i>Metzgeria furcata</i>									17-1	17-1	40-1	43-2
<i>Cardamine hirsuta</i>											10-1	7-1
<i>Corydalis pumila</i>										50-1	30-1	
<i>Glechoma hederacea</i>											30-1	
<i>Hepatica nobilis</i>									17-1	17-1		64-1
<i>Polygonatum odoratum</i>										17-1		21-1
<i>Silene nutans</i>										17-1	10-1	14-1
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>		20-1						22-1	17-1	17-1	70-1	50-1
<i>Holcus mollis</i>										33-1		7-1
<i>Melica nutans</i>				17-1	13-1	9-1				17-1	10-1	64-1
<i>Isoetes myurum</i>										33-2	20-1	14-1
<i>Radula complanata</i>										17-1	10-1	36-1
<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i>				17-5					67-3			7-1
<i>Calluna vulgaris</i>						18-1			33-1			7-3
<i>Botrychium lunaria</i>	8-1	20-1			13-1					17-1		7-1
<i>Inula salicina</i>								11-1		17-1		20-1
<i>Stellaria graminea</i>		20-1										
<i>Abietinella abietina</i>			20-1	13-1		18-1	13-1			17-1		
<i>Mnium cuspidatum</i>	25-1	40-1	60-1	33-1		55-1	25-1	56-1	33-1	17-1	40-1	
<i>Scelopodium purum</i>					25-1	9-1		11-1				
<i>Tortella flavovirens+spp.</i>	8-1		80-2		25-1	36-1	25-1	11-1		33-2		14-1
<i>Cladonia furcata</i>	58-2	20-1	60-1	17-1	13-1		25-1		33-2			
<i>Cladonia rangiformis</i>	35-2	40-2	20-1		13-1	36-1	63-1	22-1	17-1	33-1		7-1

Additional species occurring in 1 or 2 of the RE-groups:

Prunus spinosa (8:13-1,6:11-1); *Empetrum nigrum* (11:7-1); *Vaccinium vitis-idaea* (11:7-1); *Achillea ptarmica* (6:11-1,5:17-1); *Agrimonia eupatoria* (11:7-1); *Arabidopsis thaliana* (4:9-1); *Dianthus deltoides* (6:11-1); *Euphrasia* spp. (9:17-1,13:10-1); *Geum rivale* (13:10-1); *Hyericum perforatum* (6:11-1); *Lathyrus pratensis* (7:13-1); *Linaria vulgaris* (13:20-1); *Plantago maritima* (9:17-1); *Polygala vulgaris* (1:20-1); *Primula veris* (4:9-1,13:10-1); *Rumex acetosella* (7:13-1); *Satureja vulgaris* (11:7-1); *Trifolium medium* (7:13-1); *Verbascum thapsus* (11:7-1); *Viola arvensis* (7:13-1); *Viola tricolor* (11:7-1); *Agrostis canina* (4:18-1); *Carex panicea* (9:17-1, 13:10-1); *Equisetum arvense* (7:25-1); *Molinia caerulea* (8:13-1, 10:17-1); *Poa compressa* (4:9-1); *Brachythecium albicans* (2:40-1); *Brachythecium velutinum* (5:17-1); *Homalothecium sericeum* (11:14-1); *Neckera pennata* (8:13-1); *Platygyrium renens* (11:14-1); *Polytrichum juniperum* (9:33-2); *Polytrichum piliferum* (9:17-1); *Tortula subulata* (13:10-1); *Cephalozia* spp. (1:20-1, 11:7-1); *Cladonia crispata* (6:11-1); *Cladonia rangiferina* (5:17-1); *Cladonia uncialis* (9:17-1); *Peltigera canina* (13:10-2).

and *Bryum argenteum*, also appear as constants. A few species characteristic of shore communities (Tyler et al. 1971) are confined to this block: *Armeria maritima*, *Cochlearia officinalis*, and *Potentilla anserina*.

Through dominance of *Festuca rubra* and rich occurrence of *Cladonia furcata* and *C. rangiformis*, block I shows affinity to the Galio-Tortuletum (Gal-Tort) cladonietosum of Hall-

berg (1971). However, the species *Carex arenaria*, *Satureja acinos*, and *Racomitrium canescens* with rich occurrence in that community are lacking in block I. The reason for this is believed to be differences in the soil. Gal-Tort is confined to sand with a sparse occurrence of shells, block I only to concentrated shell-beds. Drifting sand does not occur on Akerøya.

Block I also shows high similarity to the 'Dune

Fig. 7. Mean height of RE-groups relative to sea level. Vertical bars represent standard deviation.

pastures' from Lista, SW Norway, described by Høiland (1978).

Block II (including RE-group No. 2). The plots making up the block are confined to a narrow zone just above block I (Fig. 7). The most easily observed difference from block I is the dominance of *Festuca ovina*, although *F. rubra* is still frequent. The most important species in the field layer are *Plantago lanceolata*, *Sedum acre*, *S.*

album, *Achillea millefolium*, and *Taraxacum* spp. Therophytes (Raunkiær 1907) play an important part; *Cerastium semidecandrum*, *Erophila verna*, and *Arenaria serpyllifolia* are constants in block II. *Anthyllis vulneraria* and *Satureja acinos* are important differential species against block I. The bottom layer is quite variable. Sometimes species from block I dominate, e.g. *Ceratodon purpureus*, *Bryum* spp., and *Hypnum cupressiforme*, but most often other species take over: *Cornicularia aculeata*, *Barbula convoluta*, and *Tortella tortuosa*. In two of the plots the bottom layer is poorly developed.

Block II must be considered to belong to the pioneer communities, but as only 5 plots make up the block, it is hard to decide whether it is a homogeneous community or should be subdivided further. The plots are from rocks with a sparse soil layer, and are characterized by high insolation and extremely xerothermous conditions. They are exposed to strong western winds so that the small tussocks of *Festuca ovina* are often standing solitarily on the naked ground as a result of wind erosion.

The block is placed in the class Sedo-Scleranthetea, but can hardly be identified with

Fig. 8. Block I vegetation on a shell-bed close to the sea. Shell-bed No. 18. 2 VI 1979.

any of Hallberg's (1971) associations. The similarity to his '*Arenaria serpyllifolia-Sedum acre* Gesellschaft' (Aren-Sed) indicates that block II may come close to a community not analysed by Hallberg (1971), replacing Aren-Sed in the outer parts of Bohuslän. Block II shows a slight similarity to the 'Kalkfelsenrasen' of Rodenberg (1976).

Block III (including RE-group No. 1). Pioneer vegetation on rocks with a thin layer of soil mixed with gastropod and *Mytilus* shells. Like block II, the insolation is high and also block III is wind exposed. Large patches without plant cover or covered with crustose lichens occur, and may be looked upon as relicts from the initial successional stage. As the cushions of mosses in the bottom layer easily dry out during periods of hot and sunny weather, the community is vulnerable to severe erosion.

Festuca ovina is even more important than in block II, and *Festuca rubra* is never dominant. Chamaephytes (Raunkjær 1907) are the most important life form in the field layer, but therophytes also have high constancies. *Sedum acre* and *Achillea millefolium* are constants; *Sagina nodosa*, *Sedum album*, *Arenaria serpyllifolia*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Hornungia petraea*, *Satureja acinos*, and *Achillea dioica* are other important species. The last one is a differential species against block II. Where a bottom layer is well developed, it consists of *Hypnum cupressiforme*, *Ceratodon purpureus*, and *Bryum argenteum* from blocks I and II, but has in addition a large number of calciphilous species such as *Ditrichum flexicaule*, *Distichium capillaceum*, *Encalypta streptocarpa*, *Myurella julacea*, *Tortula ruralis*, and *Barbula convoluta*.

Block III corresponds to the alliance Tortello-Sedion of Hallberg (1971), and includes elements of both of his closely related associations. *Sedum album* associates block III with Sedo-Tortelletum while *Antennaria dioica* is typical of Ditricho-Sedetum.

Similar vegetation is described from many areas within Scandinavia. Block III corresponds to the association Sedetum acris of Marker (1967, 1969) and to the alliance Sedo-Scleranthion of Sunding (1963), most closely resembling his association Sedetum acris. The '*Sedum acre-Toninia coeruleo-nigricans* community' of Kleiven (1959) may be regarded as similar, but also includes the preceding successional stage to block III dominated by crustose lichens.

From Sweden, similar vegetation is described

by Albertson (1946, 1950) from the alvar areas. Block III corresponds to the Sedetum tortellosum. '*Sedum album-Tortella inclinata* - Soziation' from Öland (Albertson 1950) and partly to Sedetum tortellosum from Västergötland (Albertson 1946). By the dominance of *Festuca ovina*, block III also approaches the 'subassociation of *Festuca-Tortella-Cetraria*' of the association Festucetum tortellosum.

The 'Kalkfelsenrasen' of Rodenberg (1976) parallel block III as regards floristical composition and ecological relationships.

Block IV (including RE-groups 9 and 8). Vegetation dominated by xerophytes on the transition between bare rocks and typical grassland. *Festuca ovina* dominates in the field layer. In 1979 the plots in the block were characterized by occasional naked patches in the bottom layer. This is most probably caused by the extremely dry summers in 1975-1977. The grazing of sheep also influences the vegetation by trampling. By the action of strong winds, loose fragments of the moss cover are easily carried away (Rosén & Sjögren 1973), exposing the underlying shells or rock. In 1979, regeneration of the moss cover had partly begun. The high constancy values of therophytes in block IV are also caused by the exposure of naked ground, easily colonized by annual species.

The elements of pioneer vegetation are *Sedum acre*, *S. album* (both less important than in block III), *Arenaria serpyllifolia*, *Satureja acinos*, *Erophila verna*, and *Hornungia petraea*. An important species with wide amplitude in xeric communities is *Antennaria dioica*.

A characteristic attribute of block IV is the occurrence of many typical grassland species. Some of them are frequent in stands of block IV vegetation. The existence of such a transitional community between the typical Sedo-Scleranthetea and Festuco-Brometea (block V) has been previously pointed out by Sunding (1963, 1965) in the description of the association Arabideto-Sedetum, classified under Sedo-Scleranthetea. Typical grassland species common in Block IV are *Potentilla erecta*, *Anthoxanthum odoratum*, *Campanula rotundifolia*, *Linum catharticum*, *Pimpinella saxifraga*, *Centaurea jacea*, *Carex ericetorum*, and *C. flacca*.

The bottom layer is, as previously noted, rarely covering the ground. The mixing of species from xeric and mesic habitats characteristic of the field layer reappears in the bottom layer. Typical

Fig. 9. The north-facing slope of shell-bed No. 31. The grazing pressure is low and the invasion of *Juniperus communis* is almost completed. 4 VI 1979.

species are *Barbula convoluta* (constant), *Tortella tortuosa*, *Ditrichum flexicaule*, *Encalypta streptocarpa*, and *Myurella julacea* from the pioneer communities and *Campylium chrysophyllum* and *Fissidens cristatus*, both constants, from the mesic habitats.

Block IV does not directly correspond to associations described by Hallberg (1971), but belongs to the class Sedo-Scleranthetea. The community most closely related to it is the 'Arenaria serpyllifolia-Sedum acre Gesellschaft'. The occurrence of many grassland species, especially *Carex ericetorum* which is regarded as a character species of the Festuco-Brometea association Fragario-Helictotricheum, indicates affinity also to this class.

The 'Festuca ovina-heaths' described by Kleiven (1959), and in particular the *Festuca ovina* facies of *Poa* (alpinae)-Anthyllisetum vulneraria described by Marker (1967, 1969), are fairly similar to block IV.

Related communities are described as 'Xerophilen Trockenrasen' (Rodenburg 1976) and as Festucetum alvarense tortellosum (Albertson 1950) from Öland and *Festuca-Tortella-Cetraria*

subassociation of Festucetum tortellosum from Västergötland (Albertson 1946).

Block V (including RE-groups No. 4, 7, and 6). Typical mesic grassland vegetation, but owing to drought occasional regression has occurred, forming bare patches now recolonized by pioneer stage mosses and therophytes.

Except for the absence of *Sedum* spp., most of the species that are found in block IV reappear in block V. In addition, a lot of species confined to Festuco-Brometea appear. They are preferential character species for the mesic grassland vegetation at Akerøya. The most important species are *Arrhenatherum pratense*, *Carex caryophyllea*, *Luzula campestris*, and *Plantago media* in the field layer and *Camptothecium lutescens* (dominant) and *Rhytidium rugosum* in the bottom layer.

The most important species for the physiognomy of the community are *Festuca ovina*, commonly covering more than 50%, *Antennaria dioica*, *Carex ericetorum*, *C. caryophyllea*, and *C. flacca*.

The community is best developed far from the sea (8–12 m above sea level, see Fig. 7), and is

dominating in the central parts of the island. The depth of the soil layer varies, but is rarely more than about 25 cm. The content of shells is also variable. Gastropod shells in all stages of degradation are characteristic to block V.

The community is analogous to the *Fragario-Helictotrichetum* of Hallberg (1971), the 'mesophilen Trockenrasen' of Rodenberg (1976), the *Avenetum pratensis* (Albertson 1946), and the *Avenetum alvarensis* of Albertson (1950).

A similar community does not seem to be described from Norway. *Poa* (alpinae)-*Anthyllis* *vulneraria*, *typicum*, described by Marker (1967, 1969), is also dominated by *Arrhenatherum pratense* and *Festuca ovina*, but otherwise there are too many floristical differences to regard this community and block V as being closely related. Sunding (1963) does not describe any community dominated by *Festuca ovina*.

Block VI (including RE-group No. 5). The block VI does not represent a community, but embraces 5 plots which either lie on the border between open grassland (block V) and *Juniperus communis*-dominated shrub or correspond to small thickets of *Juniperus communis* expanding in typical block V vegetation. The species composition of the block must be regarded as a more or less random collection of block V and block VII species, and will not be dealt with separately.

Block VII (including RE-groups No. 10, 13, and 11) is the vegetation of areas that have been too insufficiently grazed by sheep to be kept open. *Juniperus communis* is the major dominant in all plots that belong to this block. *Juniperus* has a strong influence on its environment as it quickly produces a thick layer of acidic litter causing a drop in pH by 1 to 2 pH-units (Skogen 1976). In addition, the bottom and field-layers are deprived of most of their light by the dense stands of *Juniperus*.

The vegetation of block VII contains many species with a high constancy in blocks IV and V, but these mostly show reduced vitality and are rarely fertile because of the shade (cf. Rodenberg 1976). Some species with centre of gravity in richer coniferous or deciduous forests (particularly the associations *Melico-Piceetum*, *Melico-Quercetum* and *Ulmo-Tilietum* in Kieland-Lund (1971)) or in marginal communities of the class *Trifolio-Gerianietea* (Sunding 1963, 1965, Marker 1967, 1969, Hallberg 1971), are confined to the *Juniperus* community when they

occur in shell-bed vegetation at Akerøya. Examples of such species are *Corydalis pumila*, *Galium boreale*, *Geranium sanguineum*, *Carex digitata*, *Deschampsia flexuosa* (mostly in poor coniferous forest types), and *Melica nutans*.

The thick litter that occurs shortly after the invasion of *Juniperus communis* makes most of the species of the bottom layer disappear. The high occurrence of some grassland- and even some pioneer mosses in block VII is due to the presence of uncovered shells and bare soil also under dense *Juniperus* shrubs. The therophyte *Hornungia petraea* may also occur on such naked shell spots.

The only moss species which is capable of growing successfully on *Juniperus* litter is *Isoetium myurum*. *Metzgeria furcata*, *Neckera complanata*, and *Radula complanata* grow on the base of *Juniperus* and on needles on the ground, and are actually members of an epiphytic synusium.

Similar vegetation has not drawn much attention in Scandinavia, probably because it is most often readily displaced by more stable communities. *Juniperus* vegetation is mentioned by Almquist (1929) and is an element of the 'Gebüsch-vegetation' described by Rodenberg (1976) from central Öland. Various *Juniperus*-dominated communities are also described from Gotland by Du Rietz (1925).

Lost units

Subjective analysis of the shell-bed vegetation of Akerøya reveals a community dominated by *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi*. The community is rare and always covers small segments. Two of the 100 plots belong to this community. But because of the low number of plots, it has not emerged as a group on its own. One of the plots was placed in RE-group 9, the other in RE-group 12, but later moved to group 5 when group 12 was abandoned.

The *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* community is confined to margins of shell-beds or more stony areas where smaller amounts of shell are deposited. Occasionally it is situated in a distinct zone between typical block V and block VII communities.

The floristic composition of the community is in many ways similar to block VII, but a few more block V species usually go into the *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* community because of its openness. The ground is covered with dried

Table IX. The *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* community. Subjectively selected relevées, 1 m² each. Constancy (%) and characteristic degree of cover (Persson 1961).

Relevée No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Shell-bed No.	7	7	7	25	25	26	26	30	31	31	
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	20-1
<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	20-1
<i>Rosa</i> spp.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	20-1
<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i>	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	100-5
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	100-1
<i>Antennaria dioica</i>	1	-	1	-	1	1	1	-	-	1	60-1
<i>Campanula rotundifolia</i>	-	1	-	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	40-1
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	40-1
<i>Galium verum</i>	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	100-1
<i>Geranium sanguineum</i>	-	-	1	2	1	1	-	-	1	1	60-1
<i>Hepatica nobilis</i>	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	20-1
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i> coll.	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	20-1
<i>Inula salicina</i>	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20-1
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	-	1	1	1	-	-	1	-	1	-	50-1
<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i>	1	1	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	90-1
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	-	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	30-1
<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20-1
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	40-1
<i>Rubus saxatilis</i>	-	1	2	-	-	1	1	1	2	1	70-1
<i>Thalictrum minus</i>	2	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	40-1
<i>Thymus pulegioides</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	20-1
<i>Vicia cracca</i>	1	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	1	60-1
<i>Viola</i> spp.	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	1	1	1	80-1
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	1	-	40-1
<i>Arrhenatherum pratense</i>	1	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	60-1
<i>Arrhenatherum pubescens</i>	1	1	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	1	60-1
<i>Briza media</i>	1	1	1	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	60-1
<i>Carex caryophylllea</i>	-	-	-	-	3	-	1	-	1	1	40-2
<i>Carex digitata</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	20-1
<i>Carex ericetorum</i>	-	1	1	-	2	-	2	-	-	-	40-2
<i>Carex flacca</i>	-	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	-	-	70-1
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	60-1
<i>Festuca ovina</i>	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	100-1
<i>Luzula campestris</i>	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	1	-	30-1
<i>Melica nutans</i>	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	40-1
<i>Poa pratensis</i> coll.	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	20-1
<i>Barbula convoluta</i>	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	20-1
<i>Dicranum scoparium</i>	-	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	30-1
<i>Fissidens cristatus</i>	-	-	1	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	40-1

Additional species occurring in 1 of the relevées (all with cover value 1):

Calluna vulgaris (8), *Agrimonia eupatoria* (2), *Anthyllis vulneraria* (7), *Centaurea jacea* (7), *Galium boreale* (9), *Hypochoeris maculata* (1), *Plantago media* (3), *Veronica chamaedrys* (9), *Veronica officinalis* (8), *Agrostis canina* (4), *Poa compressa* (5), *Sieglingia decumbens* (4), *Bryum* spp. (3), *Hypnum cupressiforme* (4), *Cladonia rangiformis* (5), *Cladonia arbuscula* coll. (7).

leaves from *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* and contains no vegetation. Ten subjectively placed relevées from the community are analysed (Table IX).

The community has a number of features in common with the field layer of Melico-Pinetum (Marker 1967) and *Arctostaphylo*-Pinetum (Sunding 1963), but lacks a tree layer. In Got-

land, the 'Nackte *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* Ass. described by Du Rietz (1925) seems to be corresponding to the *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* community described here. Du Rietz (1925: 28) states that the community appears at boulder-drifts near the shore and at the Alvar in a mosaic with *Juniperus* shrub and open grassland communities.

Successional relationships of the shell-bed vegetation

The description of successions in the shell-bed vegetation relies partly on investigations by other authors – particularly Hallberg (1971), Rosén & Sjögren (1973), and Rodenborg (1976) – and partly on observations of zonation and sheep behaviour during field work at Akerøya in 1979.

A survey of successional relationships between the major blocks is given in Fig. 10.

Two series of primary successions are found on the shell-beds of Akerøya, both of them being xeroseres in the sense of Eyre (1968).

Shortly after the elevation of the shell-beds above the upper limit for direct influence by the sea, the block I vegetation is established. A bottom layer will develop gradually as soil is accumulated. With high grazing pressure and much trampling, the development of a closed bottom layer will be retarded (Hallberg 1971). If the influences of grazing are moderate, however, the shore-line displacement gradually causes an elevation and a leaching of salts from the shell-beds, causing *Festuca ovina* to replace *F. rubra* as the dominating species. A community resembling the association Galio-Festucetum described by Hallberg (1971) may develop, but is not found in its typical form at Akerøya. Instead, *Juniperus communis* invades the shell-beds, establishing block VII vegetation. Many of the species characteristic to block I occur in RE-group 13. From Fig. 7 one can see that RE-group 13 is found as low as 2 m above sea level.

The other xerosere starts at naked rocks with scattered shells in crevices. Via an initial stage of crustose lichens, communities of block II and block III types are established. The relation between these two blocks is obscure due to low representation in the sample set. By accumulation of soil, these xeric communities develop into block IV vegetation, as described by Rosén & Sjögren (1973) and Rodenborg (1976). These authors, as well as Hallberg (1971), hold that the community will be stable in slopes with southern exposition due to the high insolation and the extremely xeric micro-climate. Intense grazing may also retard further development, while a moderate grazing intensity is assumed to cause a transition into block V by gradual appearance of typical block V species (Hallberg 1971). In places sheltered from grazing and strong winds, the block IV community is rapidly overgrown by

Fig. 10. Major successional relationships of shell-bed communities at Akerøya.

Juniperus communis and a block VII community is formed.

The block V community is dependent on grazing by sheep not to be overgrown by *Juniperus communis* (cf. Hallberg 1971). It therefore represents a disclimax in the American terminology (Krebs 1978), a plagioclimax in the sense of the English school of vegetation dynamics (Eyre 1968).

At Akerøya the block V community is mainly distributed in the central parts, totally dominating in shell-beds 5–16 (Fig. 2). This is close to the abandoned farmland, and is one of the most important areas for grazing. The sheep prefer to stay in this area, and create a grazing pressure sufficient to avoid the invasion of *Juniperus communis*. The mechanism involved is assumed to be complex (Rosén & Sjögren 1973), but probably involves the eating of the seedlings of *Juniperus* in spring. If grazing is abandoned,

Fig. 11. Prostrate *Juniperus communis* in exposed and intensively grazed shell-bed dominated by block V vegetation. Small naked patches are visible among the tussocks of *Festuca ovina*. In the background abrupt transition into *Calluna*-heath. Shell-bed No. 5. 2 VI 1979.

Juniperus propagates from the colonies that occur in the pasture, initiating a rapid expansion (Skogen 1976).

When block VII is established, block V communities can only be produced by burning and clearing the shrubs away. But extreme drought and exceptionally high grazing pressure may cause the death of *Juniperus* (Fig. 12). Rosén & Sjögren (1973) have observed that when the grazing intensity exceeds an upper threshold, the sheep will start eating the weak shoots of *Juniperus*, eventually causing its death. By the death of *Juniperus*, the ground is laid open to wind erosion, and a block IV community finally regenerates. This regressive succession was observed in many places at Akerøya in 1979, always taking place on shallow soil, and is mainly caused by the dry summers of 1975–1977.

The effects of drought and overgrazing on communities resembling blocks IV and V on the Great Alvar of Öland were investigated by Rosén & Sjögren (1973). High grazing and trampling intensity causes fragmentation of the bottom layer. The loose parts easily blow away during dry and windy periods, causing naked spots to

appear between the *Festuca ovina* tussocks. Regeneration of the vegetation starts at the tussocks, thus leaving the interjacent naked spots without vegetation for many years. Regeneration of the bottom layer starts with a number of pioneer mosses. The most important are *Bryum argenteum*, *Barbula convoluta*, *Tortella tortuosa*, *T. fragilis*, and *Ditrichum flexicaule*. In the field layer, drought resistant therophytes like *Hornungia petraea*, *Erophila verna*, *Saxifraga tridactylites*, *Arenaria serpyllifolia*, and *Cerastium semidecandrum* may appear. Most of these species are held by Hallberg (1971) and Rodenborg (1976) to be characteristic of pioneer communities of the class Sedo-Scleranthetea.

The climax vegetation of most shell-beds at Akerøya is believed to be the *Juniperus communis*-dominated block VII community. *Prunus spinosa* has replaced *Juniperus communis* in a few protected places. Similarly, prostrate *Picea abies* occurs in a couple of shell-beds. From Bohuslän (Hallberg 1971) *Quercus robur*, *Corylus avellana*, *Populus tremula*, partly *Picea abies*, and *Pinus sylvestris* are reported to replace *Juniperus communis* over time. It is not

Fig. 12. *Juniperus communis* in shell-bed strongly eroded by grazing and drought. Shell-bed No. 19. 2 VI 1979.

possible to decide whether the exposure to strong south-westerly winds at Akerøya during most of the year is sufficient to keep trees away. According to Ivarsson (1962), the outer areas of Bohuslän have not been covered with forests for at least 300 years, but whether the trees at some time reached the sea in exposed localities is not known. Today, small fragments of forests occur only in the most protected valleys in the eastern parts of Akerøya. It remains to be seen if trees will invade the shell-beds of Akerøya.

Conclusion

Association analysis has been employed as a first approach to classification of shell-bed vegetation. Reallocation was carried out on untransformed and square root transformed Hult-Sernander-Du Rietz cover values. The three sets of classifications thus obtained were evaluated by means of position vectors ordination. Application of reallocation to the ASS-groups improved the classification when the criteria of Williams & Dale (1965) were used as basis for

evaluation. The best result was obtained by untransformed cover values.

The number of plots, crucial to the outcome of the classification, was subjectively chosen as 100 for the present study. Most of the groups produced proved easy to interpret, but a couple of groups with 3 and 5 plots were impossible to relate to communities described by other authors because of their high internal heterogeneity.

Comparison with other studies in shell-bed vegetation (Hallberg 1971) or vegetation with similar ecological conditions (see p. 83 for references) shows that most RE-groups are easily related to associations described by other authors. A further division in communities of lower rank was not possible with a data set consisting of only 100 squares.

Application of ordination *in series* with association analysis and reallocation has given promising results, and should be well suited for studies of vegetation rich in species.

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